

Supplementary Materials

The Role of Supporting and Disruptive Mechanisms of FT3 Homeostasis in Regulating the Hypothalamic-Pituitary-Thyroid Axis

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Mathematical Model

The mathematical model consists of a system of four coupled first-order parametrized nonlinear ordinary differential equations (ODEs), which were developed to account for the interdependencies between the four hormones TRH, TSH, FT4 and FT3 in the network of the hypothalamic-pituitary-thyroid (HPT) axis regulation. While TRH and TSH feed forward to the pituitary and thyroid, respectively, FT4 and FT3 feed back to both the pituitary and hypothalamus. FT4 is converted to its biologically more active sister hormone FT3 through a partly TSH-dependent multi-enzyme process.

The new mechanistic model is an augmentation of our published minimal model (1). Additionally, it constructs the essential mechanisms described by the earlier study (1), using physiologically realistic production rate constants, binding affinities of the hormones to the relevant receptor and saturation effects. This is a representation of a mechanistic model. The rationale of our approach is based on relational stability where the limbs of feedback loops respond to each (2). The solution of the ODE system provides a stable equilibrium state for each hormone and a conditional balance between the loop influences or the ratio of the strengths of the interdependent loops. With appropriate scaling based on fractions of the normal levels of the hormones, the present model and the minimal model (system sys. 10) (1) are comparable (Supplementary Figure 1).

Supplementary Figure 1. Comparison of model predictions between A) the present mechanistic model and B) our published minimal model (1). FT3 levels are better protected, compared to the levels of FT4 and TSH in both models as the FT4 production rate varies. C) The two models show high congruence. We note that, while the mechanistic model uses actual units of the respective hormones in other figures, this comparison is based on fractions, where 1 equals the normal reference level for a euthyroid person. Details and code to produce the figure are provided below.

ODE system of the mechanistic model

$$\frac{d[TRH]}{dt} = k_{11} \cdot \frac{1}{v_{12} \cdot (\frac{K}{c_f} + [FT4]) + (1 - v_{12}) \cdot (\frac{K}{c_f} + [FT3])} - a_1 \cdot [TRH] \quad (\text{eq. 1})$$

$$\frac{d[TSH]}{dt} = k_{21} \cdot [TRH] \cdot sp(TSH) \cdot \frac{1}{v_{22} \cdot (\frac{K}{c_f} + [FT4]) + (1 - v_{22}) \cdot (\frac{K}{c_f} + [FT3])} - a_2 \cdot [TSH] \quad (\text{eq. 2})$$

$$\frac{d[FT4]}{dt} = k_{31} \cdot [TSH] - a_3 \cdot [FT4] \quad (\text{eq. 3})$$

$$\frac{d[FT3]}{dt} = k_{41} \cdot [FT4] + k_{42} \cdot [FT4] \cdot [TSH] + k_{43} \cdot [TSH] - a_4 \cdot [FT3] \quad (\text{eq.4})$$

Notations

$$k_{11} = v_{11} \cdot q_1 \cdot H \cdot u$$

$$k_{21} = q_2 \cdot P$$

$$sp(TSH) = \frac{TSH_{max} - TSH}{TSH_{max} - TSH_{min}}$$

$$k_{31} = v_0 \cdot q_3 T$$

$$k_{41} = v_2 \cdot gdp$$

$$k_{42} = v_{31} \cdot gdT$$

$$v_{31} = \frac{atan(\frac{v_0}{ep1})}{2 \cdot atan(1)}$$

$$k_{43} = v_{32} \cdot q_4 T$$

$$v_{32} = \frac{atan(\frac{v_0}{ep2})}{2 \cdot atan(1)}$$

List of parameters

Coefficient	Explanation	Organ	Numerical Value
u	central brain signals	Brain	5e-9
q1	production rate of a TRH producing cell	hypothalamus	5e-17 mol/s

Coefficient	Explanation	Organ	Numerical Value
H	hypothalamic size, number of TRH-producing cells	hypothalamus	2e8
q₂	production rate of a pituitary thyrotroph	pituitary	1.5e-9 mIU/s
P	pituitary size, number of TSH-producing cells	pituitary	2e8
q_{3T}	production rate of FT4 by the thyroid	thyroid	1e-17 mol/s
gdp	T4 to T3 conversion rate by peripheral tissues	various organs	1e-6 mol/s
gdT	T4 to T3 conversion rate by the thyroid	thyroid	1.995e-7 mol/s
Kd	affinity constant of the nuclear T3 receptor for T3	hypothalamus, pituitary	1e-11 mol/L
cf	concentration factor for intracellular T3	hypothalamus, pituitary	1e3
q_{4T}	secretion rate for FT3	thyroid	2.25e-18 mol/s
v₁₁	fraction	hypothalamus	1
v₁₂	fraction	hypothalamus	0.493
v₂₂	fraction	pituitary	0.66
d₄₁	fraction	various organs	1
v₀	fraction	thyroid	1
a₁	elimination rate for TRH	hypothalamus, circulation	5e2 /s
a₂	elimination rate for TSH	pituitary, circulation	1.4e2 /s
a₃	elimination rate for FT4	circulation	1e-6 /s
a₄	elimination rate for FT3	circulation	8e-6 /s

Values are adopted estimates, based on previously reported parameters from the literature and other molecular models (3-8).

Solving the ODE system

To solve the initial value problems of the ODE system and accurately derive the equilibrium solutions for the steady state of the ODE system, we relied on MATLAB (MathWorks, Natick, MA, USA). The original solutions are obtained by using the highly accurate numerical continuation software MATLAB continuation toolbox CL MATCONTL (9). For more information refer to <http://uah.edu/faculty/pekker>. To make them easily reproducible, we port the ODE system below to the open source R programming environment, version 4.2.1 for Mac (10) with the added packages deSolve 1.32 (11) and rootSolve 1.8.2.3 (11), available from <https://www.R-project.org/>. We include the figures produced by a standard initial value solver (long time integration to find asymptotically stable equilibrium solutions of our ODE system), which is sufficiently accurate for the purposes of this paper. For successful execution, users are expected to be familiar with R programming language and have the required packages installed. We note the time for executing the code may be prolonged depending on the R version and computing capacity of the user. For numerical computation of the equilibrium solutions, hormone concentrations are scaled in the ODEs. The R scripts are provided below.

References

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R code to solve the ODE system and produce the Figures

Figure 2

```
# helper function for solving the IVP of the ODE system
f1=function(t,y,k){
  with (as.list(c(y,k)), {
    # scaling
    TRH=1.009208e-08; TSH=1.455002; FT4=1.415815e-11; FT3=5.00e-12;
```

```

# saturation function for TSH

ep=0.01;

step_up=((atan((v0-1)/ep))/(2*atan(1))+1)/2;

step_down=1-step_up;

TSHn_min=1.119; TSHn_max=100;

sp1a=(TSHn_max-TSHn)/(TSHn_max-TSHn_min);

sp1b=1;

sp1=sp1a;

sp1=step_down*sp1a+step_up*sp1b;

# saturation function for thyroidal T3 production with declining thyroid reserve

ep1=0.05;

ep2=0.04;

v42a=(atan(v0/ep1))/(2*atan(1));

v42b=1;

v42=step_down*v42a+step_up*v42b;

v43a=(atan(v0/ep2))/(2*atan(1));

v43b=1;

v43=step_down*v43a+ step_up*v43b;

# notations

k11=v11*q1*H*u/TRH;

k12=v12*(Kd/cf+FT4);

k13=(1-v12)*(Kd/cf+FT3);

k21=q2*P*TRH*sp1/TSH;

k22=v22*(Kd/cf+FT4);

k23=(1-v22)*(Kd/cf+FT3);

k31=v0*q3T*TSH/FT4;

k41=d41*gdp*FT4/FT3;

k42=d42*v42*gdT*FT4*TSH/FT3;

```

```

k43=d43*v43*q4T*TSH/FT3;

# ODEs

dTRHn=k11/(k12*FT4n+k13*FT3n)-a1*TRHn;
dTSHn=k21*TRHn/(k22*FT4n+k23*FT3n)-a2*TSHn;
dFT4n=k31*TSHn-a3*FT4n;
dFT3n=k41*FT4n+k42*FT4n*TSHn+k43*TSHn-a4*FT3n;
return(list(c(dTRHn,dTSHn,dFT4n,dFT3n)))
})
}

# list of parameters
k=list(v0=1,d41=1,d42=1,d43=1,v11=1,v12=0.493,v22=0.66,q1=5e-17,H=2e8,u=5e-9,q2=1.5e-
9,P=2e8,Kd=1e-11,cf=1e3,q3T=1e-17,gdp=2e-6,gdT=1.995e-7,q4T=2.25e-18,
a1=5e2,a2=140,a3=1e-6,a4=8e-6);

# initial values for the scaled variables
y0=c(TRHn=1,TSHn=1,FT4n=1,FT3n=1);

# helper function to return the equilibrium solutions for the hormones
fs2= function(p) {
s1 <- steady(y=y0,func=f1,parms=p,method="runsteady")
return(data.frame(TRH=s1$y[1]*10.09,TSH=s1$y[2]*1.455,FT4=s1$y[3]*14.55,FT3=s1$y[4]*5.00))
}

# equilibrium solutions
fs2(k)

      TRH   TSH   FT4   FT3
9.441342 1.627619 16.62134 5.138171

# helper function to vary selected parameters
fs3=function(pars) {
pars=pars
n=500

```

```

list1=rep(list(k),n)

listp=list()

for (i in 1:length(pars)) {

listp[[i]]=seq(pars[[i]][1],pars[[i]][2],length.out=n);

names(listp)[i]=names(pars)[i];

list1= list1 %>% map2(listp[[i]],~assign_in(.x,names(listp)[i],.y))

list2 = list1 %>% map(fs2)

dt2=bind_rows(list2)

dtp=bind_cols(listp)

dt2=cbind(dt2,dtp)

}

return(dt2)

}

# name the parameters to vary and provide their ranges

pars <- list(v0 = c(0.01,1);

# get equilibrium solutions

dt21=fs3(pars)

head(dt21)

# Figures

# Fig. 2A hypo

# helper function for plotting

fp3=function(dt2) {

dt2=dt2

nn=names(dt2)[5]

par1=dt2[,nn]

p21=ggplot() +

geom_point(aes(x= par1,y= FT3),data=dt2,colour= '#33ff00',size= 0.5) +

```

```
geom_point(aes(x= par1,y= FT4),data=dt2,colour= '#0066ff',size= 0.5) +
geom_point(aes(x= par1,y= TSH),data=dt2,size= 0.5) +
theme_classic() +
xlab(label= nn) +
ylab(label= 'Concentration')+
ylim(0,25)
p21
}
# solve equilibria and plot for parameter choice
pars <- list(v0 = c(0.001,1));
dt21=fs3(pars)
head(dt21)
p21=fp3(dt21)
p21
# Fig. 2B hyper
rm(dt21,p21)
# update parameters, solve and plot
pars <- list(v0 = c(1,15));
dt21=fs3(pars)
head(dt21)
p21=fp3(dt21)
p21+
ylim(0,50)
# Fig. 2C hypo
# update parameters, solve and plot
rm(dt21,p21)
pars <- list(v0 = c(0.01,1));
dt21=fs3(pars)
```

```
head(dt21)

# plot 2C

fp3mod=function(dt2) {

dt2=dt2

p21=ggplot() +

geom_point(aes(x= TSH,y= FT3),data=dt2,colour= '#33ff00',size= 0.5) +

geom_point(aes(x= TSH,y= FT4),data=dt2, colour= '#0066ff',size= 0.5) +

theme_classic() +

xlab(label="TSH (mIU/l)") +

ylab(label= 'Concentration (pmol/l)')+

xlim(0,15)+

ylim(0,25)

p21

}

p21=fp3mod(dt21)

p21

# Fig. 2D hyper

# update parameters

rm(dt21,p21)

pars <- list(v0 = c(1,10));

dt21=fs3(pars)

head(dt21)

fp3mod=function(dt2) {

dt2=dt2

p21=ggplot() +

geom_point(aes(x= TSH,y= FT3),data=dt2,colour= '#33ff00',size= 0.5) +

geom_point(aes(x= TSH,y= FT4),data=dt2, colour= '#0066ff',size= 0.5) +

theme_classic() +
```

```

xlab(label="TSH (mIU/l)") +
ylab(label= 'Concentration (pmol/l)')+
xlim(0,2)+
ylim(0,50)

p21
}

p21=fp3mod(dt21)

p21
# Fig. 3A, B

# enter parameters

rm(pars,dt21,dt22,dt23)

pars <- list(v0=c(0.01,3),d42=c(1,1),d43=c(1,1));

dt21=fs3(pars)

head(dt21)

rm(pars)

pars <- list(v0=c(0.01,3),d42= c(0.5,0.5),d43=c(0.5,0.5));

dt22=fs3(pars)

head(dt22)

rm(pars)

pars <- list(v0=c(0.01,3),d42=c(0,0),d43=c(0,0));

dt23=fs3(pars)

head(dt23)

# plot 3A

p3a=ggplot() +

geom_point(aes(x=TSH,y= FT3),data=dt21,colour= '#33ff00',size= 0.5) +

geom_point(aes(x=TSH,y= FT3),data=dt22,colour= 'darkolivegreen3',size= 0.5) +

geom_point(aes(x=TSH,y= FT3),data=dt23,colour= 'darkgreen',size= 0.5) +

theme_classic() +

```

```

xlab(label="TSH (mIU/l)") +
ylab(label= 'FT3 Concentration (pmol/l)')+
xlim(0,15)+
ylim(0,7)

p3a

# plot 3B

p3b=ggplot() +
geom_point(aes(x=FT4,y= TSH),data=dt21,colour= 'black',size= 0.5) +
geom_point(aes(x=FT4,y= TSH),data=dt22,colour= 'grey',size= 0.5) +
geom_point(aes(x=FT4,y= TSH),data=dt23,colour= 'darkgrey',size= 0.5) +
theme_classic() +
xlab(label="FT4 (pmol/l)") +
ylab(label= 'TSH (mIU/l)')+
xlim(0,25)+
ylim(0,15)

p3b

# Fig. 3C, D
# enter parameters

rm(pars,dt21,dt22,dt23,p21,p22,p23)

pars <- list(v0=c(0.01,3),v22=c(0.66,0.66));      # FT4 fraction 0.66

dt21=fs3(pars)

head(dt21)

rm(pars)

pars <- list(v0=c(0.01,3),v22=c(1,1));          # FT4 only feedback

dt22=fs3(pars)

head(dt22)

rm(pars)

```

```
pars <- list(v0=c(0.01,3),v22=c(0,0));          # FT3 only feedback
dt23=fs3(pars)
head(dt23)
# plot 3C
p3c=ggplot() +
geom_point(aes(x=TSH,y= FT3),data=dt21,colour= '#33ff00',size= 0.5) +
geom_point(aes(x=TSH,y= FT3),data=dt22,colour= 'darkgreen',size= 0.5) +
geom_point(aes(x=TSH,y= FT3),data=dt23,colour= 'darkolivegreen3',size= 0.5) +
theme_classic() +
xlab(label="TSH (mIU/l)") +
ylab(label= 'FT3 Concentration (pmol/l)')+
xlim(0,15)+
ylim(0,10)
p3c
# plot 3D
p3d=ggplot() +
geom_point(aes(x=FT4,y= TSH),data=dt21,colour= 'black',size= 0.5) +
geom_point(aes(x=FT4,y= TSH),data=dt22,colour= 'darkgrey',size= 0.5) +
geom_point(aes(x=FT4,y= TSH),data=dt23,colour= 'lightgrey',size= 0.5) +
theme_classic() +
xlab(label="FT4 (pmol/l)") +
ylab(label= 'TSH (mIU/l)')+
xlim(0,25)+
ylim(0,16)
p3d
```

```
# Fig. 3E

# enter parameters

rm(pars,dt21,dt22,dt23)

pars <- list(v0=c(0.01,3), d42=c(1,1),d43=c(1,1));

dt21=fs3(pars)

head(dt21)

rm(pars)

pars <- list(v0=c(0.01,3), d42=c(0,0),d43=c(0,0));

dt22=fs3(pars)

head(dt22)

rm(pars)

pars <- list(v0=c(0.01,3), d42=c(0,0),d43=c(2,2));

dt23=fs3(pars)

head(dt23)

# plot 3E

p3e=ggplot() +

geom_point(aes(x=TSH,y= FT3),data=dt21,colour= '#33ff00',size= 0.5) +

geom_point(aes(x=TSH,y= FT3),data=dt22,colour= 'darkgreen',size= 0.5) +

geom_point(aes(x=TSH,y= FT3),data=dt23,colour= 'cyan',size= 0.5) +

theme_classic() +

xlab(label="TSH (mIU/l)") +

ylab(label= 'FT3 Concentration (pmol/l)')+

xlim(0,15)+

ylim(0,7)

p3e
```

```

# Fig. 3F, G, H

# No drug    original model

rm(pars,dt21,dt22,dt23)

pars <- data.frame(v0=c(0.7,1.5));

dt21=fs3(pars)

p21=fp3(dt21)

p21

# drug models

# modify f1 to account for the drugs

f1d=function(t,y,k){
  with (as.list(c(y,k)), {
    # scaling

    TRH=1.009208e-08; TSH=1.455002; FT4=1.415815e-11; FT3=5.00e-12;

    # saturation function for TSH

    ep=0.01;

    step_up=((atan((v0-1)/ep))/(2*atan(1))+1)/2;

    step_down=1-step_up;

    TSHn_min=1.119; TSHn_max=100;

    sp1a=(TSHn_max-TSHn)/(TSHn_max-TSHn_min);

    sp1b=1;

    sp1=sp1a;

    sp1=step_down*sp1a+step_up*sp1b;

    # saturation function for thyroidal T3 production with declining thyroid reserve

    ep1=0.05;

    ep2=0.04;

    v42a=(atan(v0/ep1))/(2*atan(1));

    v42b=1;
  }
}

```

```

v42=step_down*v42a+step_up*v42b;
v43a=(atan(v0/ep2))/(2*atan(1));
v43b=1;
v43=step_down*v43a+ step_up*v43b;
# notations
k11=v11*q1*H*u/TRH;
k12=v12*(Kd/cf+FT4);
k13=(1-v12)*(Kd/cf+FT3);
k21=q2*P*TRH*sp1/TSH;
k22=v22*(Kd/cf+FT4);
k23=(1-v22)*(Kd/cf+FT3);
drug4=v0*q3T*TSH/FT4;
k41=d41*gdp*FT4/FT3;
k42=d42*gdT*FT4*TSH/FT3;
drug3=d43*q4T*TSH/FT3;
# ODEs
dTRHn=k11/(k12*FT4n+k13*FT3n)-a1*TRHn;
dTSHn=k21*TRHn/(k22*FT4n+k23*FT3n)-a2*TSHn;
dFT4n=drug4-a3*FT4n;
dFT3n=k41*FT4n+drug3-a4*FT3n;
return(list(c(dTRHn,dTSHn,dFT4n,dFT3n)))
})
}
# list of parameters
k=list(v0=1,d41=1,d42=0,d43=1,v11=1,v12=0.493,v22=0.66,q1=5e-17,H=2e8,u=5e-9,q2=1.5e-
9,P=2e8,Kd=1e-11,cf=1e3,q3T=1e-17,gdp=2e-6,gdT=1.995e-7,q4T=2.25e-
18,a1=5e2,a2=140,a3=1e-6,a4=8e-6);
# initial values for the scaled variables

```

```

y0=c(TRHn=1,TSHn=1,FT4n=1,FT3n=1);

# helper function to return the equilibrium solutions for the hormones

fs2= function(p) {

s1 <- steady(y=y0,func=f1d,parms=p,method="runsteady")

return(data.frame(TRH=s1$y[1]*10.09,TSH=s1$y[2]*1.455,FT4=s1$y[3]*14.55,FT3=s1$y[4]*5.00))

}

fs2(k)

      TRH    TSH    FT4    FT3
10.88656 2.131287 14.87179 4.024231

# T4 drug    vary v0 the external constant T4 production rate

# enter range

rm(dt22,p22,p2,dt3,p3)

pars2 <- data.frame(v0=c(0.7,1.5));

dt22=fs3(pars2)

p22=fp3(dt22)

p22

# 3F

p3f=ggplot() +

geom_point(aes(x=v0,y= FT3),data=dt21,colour= '#33ff00',size= 0.5) +

geom_point(aes(x=v0,y= FT4),data=dt21,colour= '#0066ff',size= 0.5) +

geom_point(aes(x=v0,y= TSH),data=dt21,colour= 'black',size= 0.5) +

geom_point(aes(x=v0,y= FT3),data=dt22,colour= 'darkgreen',size= 0.5) +

geom_point(aes(x=v0,y= FT4),data=dt22,colour= 'lightblue',size= 0.5) +

geom_point(aes(x=v0,y= TSH),data=dt22,colour= 'grey',size= 0.5) +

theme_classic() +

xlab(label="v0") +

```

```

ylab(label= 'Concentration')+
xlim(0.7,1.5)+
ylim(0,25)
p3f
# T4 T3 drug vary v0 + d43 to vary the external constant production rates for T4 and T3
# enter ranges
rm(dt23,p23,dt4,p4)
pars3 <- data.frame(v0=c(0.7,1.5),d43=c(5,5));
dt23=fs3(pars3)
p23=fp3(dt23)
p23
# enter range T4 drug only for comparison
rm(dt24,p24,p4,dt14,p24)
pars4 <- data.frame(v0=c(0.7,1.5),d43=c(0,0));
dt24=fs3(pars4)
p24=fp3(dt24)
p24
# 3G
p3g=ggplot() +
geom_point(aes(x=v0,y= FT3),data=dt23,colour= 'darkolivegreen3',size= 0.5) +
geom_point(aes(x=v0,y= FT4),data=dt23,colour= 'darkblue',size= 0.5) +
geom_point(aes(x=v0,y= TSH),data=dt23,colour= 'darkgrey',size= 0.5) +
geom_point(aes(x=v0,y= FT3),data=dt24,colour= 'darkgreen',size= 0.5) +
geom_point(aes(x=v0,y= FT4),data=dt24,colour= 'lightblue',size= 0.5) +
geom_point(aes(x=v0,y= TSH),data=dt24,colour= 'grey',size= 0.5) +

```

```

theme_classic() +
xlab(label="v0") +
ylab(label= 'Concentration')+
xlim(0.7,1.5)+
ylim(0,25)

p3g

# T3 drug    keep v0= very small + vary d43 to vary the external constant T3 production
rate

# enter ranges
rm(dt25,p25)
pars5 <- data.frame(v0=c(0,0.1), d43=c(1,50));
dt25=fs3(pars5)
p25=fp3(dt25)
p25
# 3H
p3h=ggplot() +
geom_point(aes(x=v0,y= FT3),data=dt25,colour= 'darkolivegreen3',size= 0.5) +
geom_point(aes(x=v0,y= FT4),data=dt25,colour= 'darkblue',size= 0.5) +
geom_point(aes(x=v0,y= TSH),data=dt25,colour= 'darkgrey',size= 0.5) +
theme_classic() +
xlab(label="v0") +
ylab(label= 'Concentration')+
xlim(0,0.1)+
ylim(0,25)
p3h

```

```
# Comparison with clinical data

# Fig. 4.

# data import dt4

# Significance testing of slopes

library(mgcv)

mod1<- gam(FT3~s(FT4TSHratio,by=group)+group,data=dt4)

anova(mod1)

# Fig. 4A

p4a=ggplot() +

geom_point(aes(x= FT4TSHratio,y= FT3,colour= group),size=0.8,data=dt4) +

geom_smooth(aes(x= FT4TSHratio,y= FT3,colour= group),data=dt4,method= 'gam')+

ylab(label = 'FT3 (pmol/l)') +

scale_colour_manual(guide= guide_legend(),breaks= c("1", "2"),labels=

c("AIT", "Ca"),values= c("blue", "red"))+

theme_classic()

p4a

# Fig. 4B,C

# import data

# copy f1 mech model

# copy fs2

# modify fs3

# function to vary multiple parameters

fs3=function(pars) {

pars=pars

n=5000      # needs to be large and split to avoid gaps
```

```

m1=0.04

m2=0.04

list1=rep(list(k),n)

listp=list()

for (i in 1:length(pars)) {

# listp[[i]]=seq(pars[[i]][1],pars[[i]][2],length.out=n);

listp[[i]]=c(seq(pars[[i]][1],m1,length.out=n/2),seq(m2,pars[[i]][2],length.out=n/2))

names(listp)[i]=names(pars)[i];

list1= list1 %>% map2(listp[[i]],~assign_in(.x,names(listp)[i],.y))

list2 = list1 %>% map(fs2)

dt2=bind_rows(list2)

dtp=bind_cols(listp)

dt2=cbind(dt2,dtp)

}

return(dt2)

}

# enter parameters

rm(dt22)

pars2 <- list(v0 = c(1e-4,2), d42=c(0,2),d43=c(0,2));

dt22=fs3(pars2)

head(dt22)

# plot 4B

p4b=ggplot() +

geom_point(aes(x=FT4,y=TSH),data=dt22,colour='#0066ff',size= 0.5) +

geom_point(aes(x=FT4,y=TSH,colour=factor(id)),data=serials5,size= 1.0) +

```

```

theme_classic() +
xlab(label= 'FT4 (pmol/l)') +
ylab(label= 'TSH (mIU/l)') +
xlim(0,30)+
ylim(0,180)

p4b

# plot 4C

p4c=ggplot() +
geom_point(aes(x=FT3,y=TSH),data=dt22,colour='#33ff00',size= 0.5) +
geom_point(aes(x=FT3,y=TSH,colour=factor(id)),data=serials5,size= 1.0) +
theme_classic() +
xlab(label= 'FT3 (pmol/l)') +
ylab(label= 'TSH (mIU/l)') +
xlim(0,6)+
ylim(0,180)

p4c

# Hyperthyroidism Graves' disease

# Fig. 4D,E

# modify f1 plus TRAb effects:

# TRAB influence on FT4 production, FT3 production, TSH feedback
f1g=function(t,y,k){
with (as.list(c(y,k)), {
# scaling

TRH=1.009208e-08; TSH=1.455002; FT4=1.415815e-11; FT3=5.00e-12;

# saturation function for TSH

ep=0.01;

```

```

step_up=((atan((v0-1)/ep))/(2*atan(1))+1)/2;
step_down=1-step_up;
TSHn_min=1.119; TSHn_max=100;
sp1a=(TSHn_max-TSHn)/(TSHn_max-TSHn_min);
sp1b=1;
sp1=sp1a;
sp1=step_down*sp1a+step_up*sp1b;
# saturation function for thyroidal T3 production with declining thyroid reserve
ep1=0.05;
ep2=0.04;
v42a=(atan(v0/ep1))/(2*atan(1));
v42b=1;
v42=step_down*v42a+step_up*v42b;
v43a=(atan(v0/ep2))/(2*atan(1));
v43b=1;
v43=step_down*v43a+ step_up*v43b;
# notations
k11=v11*q1*H*u/TRH;
k12=v12*(Kd/cf+FT4);
k13=(1-v12)*(Kd/cf+FT3);
k21=q2*P*TRH*sp1/TSH;
k22=3*TRAB*v22*(Kd/cf+FT4);
k23=(1-v22)*(Kd/cf+FT3);
k31=v0*q3T*TSH/FT4+v0*q3T*c0*TRAB/FT4;;
k41=d41*gdp*FT4/FT3;
k42=d42*v42*gdT*FT4*TSH/FT3+d42*gdT*FT4*c42*TRAB/FT3;
k43=d43*v43*q4T*TSH/FT3+d43*q4T*c43*TRAB/FT3;
# ODEs

```

```

dTRHn=k11/(k12*FT4n+k13*FT3n)-a1*TRHn;
dTSHn=k21*TRHn/(k22*FT4n+k23*FT3n)-a2*TSHn;
dFT4n=k31*TSHn-a3*FT4n;
dFT3n=k41*FT4n+k42*FT4n*TSHn+k43*TSHn-a4*FT3n;
return(list(c(dTRHn,dTSHn,dFT4n,dFT3n)))
})
}
# list of parameters
k=list(c0=1,c42=0.035,c43=0.035,TRAB=5,v0=1,d41=1,d42=1,d43=1,v11=1,v12=0.493,v22=0.66,
q1=5e-17,H=2e8,u=5e-9,q2=1.5e-9,P=2e8,Kd=1e-11,cf=1e3,q3T=1e-17,gdp=2e-6,gdT=1.995e-
7,q4T=2.25e-18, a1=5e2,a2=140,a3=1e-6,a4=8e-6);
# initial values for the scaled variables
y0=c(TRHn=1,TSHn=1,FT4n=1,FT3n=1);
# helper function to return the equilibrium solutions for the hormones
fs2= function(p) {
s1 <- steady(y=y0,func=f1g,parms=p,method="runsteady")
return(data.frame(TRH=s1$y[1]*10.09,TSH=s1$y[2]*1.455,FT4=s1$y[3]*14.55,FT3=s1$y[4]*5.00))
}
# equilibrium solutions
fs2(k)
      TRH    TSH    FT4    FT3
13.83214 0.258719 11.83561 3.043668
# function to vary multiple parameters
fs3=function(pars) {
pars=pars
n=1000
list1=rep(list(k),n)

```

```

listp=list()
for (i in 1:length(pars)) {
listp[[i]]=seq(pars[[i]][1],pars[[i]][2],length.out=n);
names(listp)[i]=names(pars)[i];
list1= list1 %>% map2(listp[[i]],~assign_in(.x,names(listp)[i],.y))
list2 = list1 %>% map(fs2)
dt2=bind_rows(list2)
dtp=bind_cols(listp)
dt2=cbind(dt2,dtp)
}
return(dt2)
}
# enter parameters
pars2 <- list(c0=c(1,20),c42=c(0.35,30),c43=c(0.35,30),TRAB=c(2,50));
dt22=fs3(pars2)
head(dt22)
# plot 4D
p4d=ggplot() +
geom_point(aes(x=FT4,y=TSH),data=dt22,colour='#0066ff',size= 0.5) +
geom_point(aes(x=FT4,y=TSH),data=gr,colour="red",size= 1.0) +
theme_classic() +
xlab(label= 'FT4 (pmol/l)') +
ylab(label="TSH (mIU/l)") +
xlim(10,50)+
ylim(0,1)

```

```

p4d
# plot 4E
p4e=ggplot() +
geom_point(aes(x=FT3,y=TSH),data=dt22,colour='#33ff00',size= 0.5) +
geom_point(aes(x=FT3,y=TSH),data=gr,colour="red",size= 1.0) +
theme_classic() +
xlab(label= 'FT3 (pmol/l)') +
ylab(label="TSH (mIU/l)") +
xlim(2,15)+
ylim(0,1)
p4e

```

Comparing the mechanistic model and the minimal model

Solving the ODE system of the mechanistic model

```

# helper function for solving the IVP of the ODE system
f1=function(t,y,k){
with (as.list(c(y,k)), {
# scaling
TRH=1.009208e-08; TSH=1.455002; FT4=1.415815e-11; FT3=5.00e-12;
# saturation function for TSH
ep=0.01;
step_up=((atan((v0-1)/ep))/(2*atan(1))+1)/2;
step_down=1-step_up;
TSHn_min=1.119; TSHn_max=100;
sp1a=(TSHn_max-TSHn)/(TSHn_max-TSHn_min);

```

```

sp1b=1;

sp1=sp1a;

sp1=step_down*sp1a+step_up*sp1b;

# saturation function for thyroidal T3 production with declining thyroid reserve

ep1=0.05;

ep2=0.04;

v42a=(atan(v0/ep1))/(2*atan(1));

v42b=1;

v42=step_down*v42a+step_up*v42b;

v43a=(atan(v0/ep2))/(2*atan(1));

v43b=1;

v43=step_down*v43a+ step_up*v43b;

# notations

k11=v11*q1*H*u/TRH;

k12=v12*(Kd/cf+FT4);

k13=(1-v12)*(Kd/cf+FT3);

k21=q2*P*TRH*sp1/TSH;

k22=v22*(Kd/cf+FT4);

k23=(1-v22)*(Kd/cf+FT3);

k31=v0*q3T*TSH/FT4;

k41=d41*gdp*FT4/FT3;

k42=d42*v42*gdT*FT4*TSH/FT3;

k43=d43*v43*q4T*TSH/FT3;

# ODEs

dTRHn=k11/(k12*FT4n+k13*FT3n)-a1*TRHn;

```

```

dTSHn=k21*TRHn/(k22*FT4n+k23*FT3n)-a2*TSHn;
dFT4n=k31*TSHn-a3*FT4n;
dFT3n=k41*FT4n+k42*FT4n*TSHn+k43*TSHn-a4*FT3n;
return(list(c(dTRHn,dTSHn,dFT4n,dFT3n)))
})
}
# list of parameters
k=list(v0=1,d41=1,d42=1,d43=1,v11=1,v12=0.493,v22=0.66,q1=5e-17,H=2e8,u=5e-
9,q2=1.5e-9,P=2e8,Kd=1e-11,cf=1e3,q3T=1e-17,gdp=2e-6,gdT=1.995e-7,q4T=2.25e-18,
a1=5e2,a2=140,a3=1e-6,a4=8e-6);
# initial values for the scaled variables
y0=c(TRHn=1,TSHn=1,FT4n=1,FT3n=1);
# helper function to return the equilibrium solutions for the hormones
fs2= function(p) {
s1 <- steady(y=y0,func=f1,parms=p,method="runsteady")
return(data.frame(TRH=s1$y[1]*10.09,TSH=s1$y[2]*1.455,FT4=s1$y[3]*14.55,FT3=s1$y[4]
*5.00))
}
# helper function to vary selected parameters
fs3=function(pars) {
pars=pars
n=500
list1=rep(list(k),n)
listp=list()
for (i in 1:length(pars)) {

```

```

listp[[i]]=seq(pars[[i]][1],pars[[i]][2],length.out=n);
names(listp)[i]=names(pars)[i];
list1= list1 %>% map2(listp[[i]],~assign_in(.x,names(listp)[i],.y))
list2 = list1 %>% map(fs2)
dt2=bind_rows(list2)
dtp=bind_cols(listp)
dt2=cbind(dt2,dtp)
}
return(dt2)
}
# plot Supplementary Figure 1
# scale hormones
TSHsc=1.455002; FT4sc=14.15815; FT3sc=5.00;
p1=ggplot() +
geom_point(aes(x= v0,y= FT3/FT3sc),data=dt21,colour= '#33ff00',size= 0.5) +
geom_point(aes(x= v0,y= FT4/FT4sc),data=dt21,colour= '#0066ff',size= 0.5) +
geom_point(aes(x= v0,y= TSH/TSHsc),data=dt21,size= 0.5) +
theme_classic()+
ylab("Concentration")+
ylim(0,2)
p1
# select parameters to vary and range for the mechanistic model
rm(dt21,p21)
pars <- list(v0 = c(0.01,1),d42 = c(1,1),d43=c(1,1));
dt21=fs3(pars)

```

```

head(dt21)

# plot the mechanistic model

p21=ggplot() +

geom_point(aes(x= v0,y= FT3),data=dt21,colour= '#33ff00',size= 0.5) +

geom_point(aes(x= v0,y= FT4),data=dt21,colour= '#0066ff',size= 0.5) +

geom_point(aes(x= v0,y= TSH),data=dt21,size= 0.5) +

theme_classic()+

ylab("Concentration (pmol/l or mIU/l)")

p21

```

Solving the ODE system of the minimal model

```

# minimal model (system sys. 10), as described by Hoermann et al. (1).

rm(fn1,k,y0,out1,,fs2,fs3)

fn1=function(t,y,k){

with (as.list(c(y,k)), {

dTRH= s1/(k134*FT4*FT3) - a1*TRH

dTSH= k21*TRH+c2/(k234*FT4*FT3) - a2*TSH

dFT4= k32*TSH - a3*FT4

dFT3= k423*TSH*FT4 + k43*FT4 + k42*TSH - a4*FT3

return(list(c(dTRH,dTSH,dFT4,dFT3)))

})

}

k=c(s1=1,k134=1,k21=1,c2=1,k234=1,k32=1,k423=1,k43=1,k42=1,a1=1,a2=1,a3=1,a4=1

)

y0=c(TRH=1,TSH=1,FT4=1,FT3=1)

times=seq(0,20, by=1)

```

```

out1=ode(y=y0,func=fn1,times=seq(0,20,by=1),parms=k)

plot(out1)

# function to find equilibria

fs2= function(p) {

s1 <- steady(y=y0,func=fn1,parms=p,method="runsteady")

return(data.frame(TRH=s1$y[1],TSH=s1$y[2],FT4=s1$y[3],FT3=s1$y[4]))

}

# helper function to vary selected parameters

fs3=function(pars) {

pars=pars

n=500

list1=rep(list(k),n)

listp=list()

for (i in 1:length(pars)) {

listp[[i]]=seq(pars[[i]][1],pars[[i]][2],length.out=n);

names(listp)[i]=names(pars)[i];

list1= list1 %>% map2(listp[[i]],~assign_in(.x,names(listp)[i],.y))

list2 = list1 %>% map(fs2)

dt2=bind_rows(list2)

dtp=bind_cols(listp)

dt2=cbind(dt2,dtp)

}

return(dt2)

}

# select parameters to vary and range for the minimal model

```

```

rm(dt22,p22)

pars2 <- list(k32=c(0.1,1),k43=c(0.7,0.7),k423=c(0.2,0.2),k42=c(0.1,0.1));

dt22=fs3(pars2)

head(dt22)

# plot minimal model

p22=ggplot() +

geom_point(aes(x= k32,y= FT3),data=dt22,colour= '#33ff00',size= 0.5) +

geom_point(aes(x= k32,y= FT4),data=dt22,colour= '#0066ff',size= 0.5) +

geom_point(aes(x= k32,y= TSH),data=dt22,size= 0.5) +

theme_classic()+

ylab("Concentration")

p22

```

Produce Supplementary Figure 1

use equilibrium solutions saved above in dt21 and dt22

scale the hormone levels for comparability between the models

place panels side-by-side

scale hormones as fractions where 1 equals the normal reference level

of a euthyroid person, with the following scaling factors

TSHscmech= 1.627619; FT4scmech= 16.62134; FT3scmech= 5.138171;

TSHscmin= 1.240356; FT4scmin= 1.240356; FT3scmin= 1.299982;

p1=ggplot() +

geom_point(aes(x= v0,y= FT3/FT3scmech),data=dt21,colour= '#33ff00',size= 0.5) +

geom_point(aes(x= v0,y= FT4/FT4scmech),data=dt21,colour= '#0066ff',size= 0.5) +

geom_point(aes(x= v0,y= TSH/TSHscmech),data=dt21,size= 0.5) +

theme_classic()+

```

xlab("Fraction of Normal FT4 Production")+
ylab("Fraction of Normal Concentration")+
ylim(0,2)

p2=ggplot() +
geom_point(aes(x= k32,y= FT3/FT3scmin),data=dt22,colour= '#33ff00',size= 0.5) +
geom_point(aes(x= k32,y= FT4/FT4scmin),data=dt22,colour= '#0066ff',size= 0.5) +
geom_point(aes(x= k32,y= TSH/TSHscmin),data=dt22,size= 0.5) +
theme_classic()+

xlab("Fraction of Normal FT4 Production")+
ylab("FRaction of Normal Concentration")+
ylim(0,2)

p2

# overlay

p3=ggplot() +
geom_point(aes(x= v0,y= FT3/FT3scmech),data=dt21,colour='#33ff00',size= 0.5) +
geom_point(aes(x= k32,y= FT3/FT3scmin),data=dt22,colour='darkgreen',size= 0.5) +
geom_point(aes(x= v0,y= FT4/FT4scmech),data=dt21,colour='blue',size= 0.5) +
geom_point(aes(x= k32,y= FT4/FT4scmin),data=dt22,colour='darkblue',size= 0.5) +
geom_point(aes(x= v0,y= TSH/TSHscmech),data=dt21,colour='black',size= 0.5) +
geom_point(aes(x= k32,y= TSH/TSHscmin),data=dt22,colour='darkgrey',size= 0.5) +
theme_classic()+

xlab("Fraction of Normal FT4 Production")+
ylab("Fraction of Normal Concentration")+
xlim(0.3,1.5)+
ylim(0,2)

```

p3

Fig. S1 Panels A mechanistic model, B minimal model, C Overlay

p123=p1+p2+p3+plot_annotation(tag_levels= 'A')

p123